

1 Predictive models for motor outcomes from deep brain
2 stimulation in Parkinson's disease: a systematic review

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20 Abstract

21 *Background*

22 Deep brain stimulation (DBS) is an effective treatment for Parkinson's disease, but the extent of
23 improvement in motor symptoms is variable. A tool which accurately predicts patient outcomes
24 based on information available pre-surgery would be useful for clinical decision-making and
25 patient expectation management. Candidate input data types to such a model include clinical
26 and cognitive measures, brain anatomy, kinematics, functional connectivity, and genetics.

27 *Objectives*

28 In this systematic review we searched for predictive models of motor outcomes from DBS. We
29 also provide a critical discussion of inputs and outputs of such models, and recommendations to
30 improve validation of models.

31 *Methods*

32 We searched the databases Web of Science, PubMed and Scopus for primary research articles
33 that tested predictions from models based on pre-surgical data and focused on motor outcomes
34 from DBS for Parkinson's disease.

35 *Results*

36 We identified 17 studies fitting these criteria. The studies with high power and generalisability
37 use only clinical data and have limited accuracy, while studies including other types of data are
38 under-powered. Predictions are mostly limited to the first year after surgery. The strongest
39 predictors across studies are age at surgery, duration of symptoms and levodopa-

40 responsiveness. We also provide conceptualization of the prediction task, summarize weak
41 points of current approaches, and discuss predictor modalities.

42 *Conclusions*

43 Further work is necessary to achieve predictive models that are ready for translation to clinical
44 practice. To achieve this goal, models and datasets should be made publicly available to enable
45 wider validation. Models should also maximise clinical utility by using interpretable inputs and
46 outputs.

47 Introduction

48 Deep brain stimulation (DBS) has been an accepted treatment for Parkinson's disease for over
49 30 years¹. It generally provides a good degree of reduction in motor symptoms, and enables
50 reduced dosage of pharmaceutical treatment. There are criteria used by clinicians to preclude
51 patients from DBS treatment, either due to concerns relating to surgical outcome, or low
52 responsiveness to dopaminergic treatment suggesting further stimulation of this network would
53 be ineffective²⁻⁴. However, amongst those who fit the criteria to receive DBS treatment, motor
54 outcomes still vary widely. Naturally, some of this variability must arise from factors during the
55 surgery, such as the surgical trajectory and accuracy with which the target structure is reached
56 ^{5,6}. The motivation behind predictive modelling of DBS outcomes is the idea that the remaining
57 variability arises from factors that are present before surgery. If we can accurately estimate the
58 degree of improvement a particular patient could expect from DBS, this would inform clinical
59 decisions about whether to proceed with surgery or alternative treatment plans, and manage
60 patient expectations.

61 The ideal predictive model would use data that is both available pre-surgery and already
62 routinely collected. It should also be clinically interpretable, providing rationale of factors that
63 influence its prediction. Ideally it should have high accuracy in predicting patient outcomes:
64 here we focus on motor outcomes but other measures such as overall quality of life and the
65 reduction in medication dosage are also important to consider^{7,8}. Further, DBS implants are
66 intended as long-term interventions, so the ideal model should be capable of predicting
67 outcomes beyond the first year after surgery. The most common targets of DBS for Parkinson's

68 are the subthalamic nucleus (STN) and the internal globus pallidus (GPi), and considering the
69 different connectivity of each of these structures, different factors may be more important for
70 predicting outcomes depending on the surgical target^{9,10}.

71 In this review we assess the state of the field of outcome prediction for motor performance
72 following DBS for Parkinson's disease using pre-surgical data. Recent developments in machine
73 learning models have led to an increase in their application in Parkinson's research¹¹. Some
74 studies have employed predictive models to optimise stimulation parameters¹²⁻¹⁵, or predict
75 outcomes using intraoperative recordings^{16,17} or the volume of tissue activated (VTA) after the
76 electrodes are placed^{12,18,19}. However, here we specifically focus on models that are candidates
77 to inform clinical decision-making before surgical intervention. We assess the published
78 candidate predictive models and make recommendations to move the field towards a predictive
79 tool that can be integrated into clinical practice.

80 We also provide a discussion of what metric of motor performance to predict and what data
81 types to use as inputs to predictive models, and provide recommendations to improve
82 validation and reproducibility of these models. These suggestions will guide the field towards
83 producing predictive models that can be deployed clinically.

84 Methods

85 The reporting of this systematic review was guided by the standards of the 2020 PRISMA
86 statement and checklist²⁰. We searched the databases Web of Science (Clarivate), PubMed
87 (NIH/NLM) and Scopus (Elsevier), on the 28th of November, 2025. The search process is
88 presented in Figure 1. In each database, the search terms were "Parkinson's" AND "deep brain

89 stimulation” AND “motor outcome” AND “prediction”. The search was limited to publications in
90 English, that were available for retrieval of full text. Inclusion criteria were that studies should
91 be primary research, focused on motor outcomes, specific to Parkinson’s disease and to deep
92 brain stimulation. Studies focused on metrics not available pre-operatively such as electrode
93 location, or using machine learning to optimise stimulation parameters were excluded. For
94 inclusion as predictive models, studies should report some metric of the accuracy of the
95 predictions of their model compared to true outcomes, rather than simply reporting group level
96 correlations ^{21,22}. For example, the co-efficient of determination (r^2) between predicted and true
97 outcomes, or the area under the curve or positive and negative predictive value for binary
98 outcomes.

99 Results

100 Results of the systematic search

101 After removal of duplicated and non-available records, we screened 84 publications for inclusion
102 eligibility (Figure 1). We excluded 10 studies which were reviews rather than primary research,
103 and we confirmed that the scope of those reviews did not overlap with this review. We excluded
104 18 studies that focused on non-motor outcomes such as quality of life, and we also excluded 19
105 studies that correlated pre-operative factors with DBS outcomes without reporting accuracy of
106 predictions from a statistical model. We excluded 8 studies that focused on using intra-operative
107 measures, and 10 which focused on optimisation of stimulation parameters following surgery.
108 We also excluded 2 studies that were not focused on Parkinson’s disease, and 3 which did not

109 concern deep brain stimulation. Altogether we included 17 studies with predictive models for
 110 motor outcomes, including 3 which were harvested from citations. These are summarised in
 111 Table 1.
 112 Our search is limited by publication bias, i.e. models with particularly low predictive accuracy
 113 are unlikely to be published and therefore would not be found by our search.

114 *Figure 1: Systematic search results. 110 records were identified across three databases. After*
 115 *removal of duplications and exclusion based on various criteria, we identified 17 studies that*
 116 *create predictive models of motor outcomes from deep brain stimulation in Parkinson's disease*
 117 *using pre-operative data.*

118 Published predictive models of motor outcomes from DBS

119 There are a range of studies reporting ‘predictors of motor outcome’ which simply correlate
120 some measure with the motor outcome on a group level, rather than constructing and testing a
121 predictive model^{21,22}. Results from these correlative studies may inform choice of factors to
122 input into a predictive model, but do not represent a testable model on their own. The studies
123 which do create a model and report some measure of its accuracy are presented in Table 1. We
124 have evaluated the parameters of each against the recommendations of Poldrack et al²², and
125 highlighted commendable aspects of each model.

126 Most of these studies are from the last 5 years, due to the recent increase in the use of machine
127 learning methods¹¹. Almost all studies also predict short-term outcomes, up to 12 months after
128 surgery. Naturally, data from longer-term follow-ups is harder to come by, but it is clinically
129 useful to predict different time scales, and importantly association studies have shown different
130 factors are associated with motor outcomes at short and long-term follow-ups²³. Notably, higher
131 levodopa responsiveness is associated with better short-term outcomes but not long-term
132 ones²⁴, and lack of vascular abnormalities and higher frontal lobe test performance are
133 associated with better long-term outcomes^{2,4,23}.

134 Across the studies presented in Table 1 there are a range of predictive models used, and several
135 publications directly compared different model types^{25–29}. Models used for classification
136 predictions include logistic regression, support vector machine, random forest, naïve Bayes, and
137 k-nearest neighbours. Models used for prediction of scalar values include support vector
138 machine, linear regression, multiple linear regression, XGBoost and LASSO. For classification, the
139 most common was logistic regression. While it was sometimes outperformed by random forest,

140 logistic regression has the benefit of being a ‘white-box’, where the factor weightings can be
141 scrutinized²⁶. For regression models, the most common were support vector machine and
142 linear/multiple linear models. Considering there is not a clear superior model amongst these
143 publications, the approach of testing several models on a dataset should continue to be
144 employed in future studies.

145 A crucial aspect of developing robust models is external validation²². Models that are built on a
146 single cohort of data are likely to over-fit to features that are present within that dataset but not
147 necessarily generalisable to the wider population. This is especially true when the cohort is
148 small, and in many of the studies in Table 1 there are less than 100 patients, some have less
149 than 50. At minimum, studies should separate a training and test dataset or use leave-one-out
150 approaches for internal validation²². Most commonly the studies in Table 1 use leave-one-out
151 approaches^{7,25,30–33}. Otherwise, some use bootstrapped repetitions of hold-out data^{7,26–29}, the
152 more conservative way to do this is ensuring each sample is used in the test data exactly once³⁴.
153 Two studies did not describe a validation method^{35,36}. Only three studies used an explicitly held-
154 out test set^{37–39}, and we only found one publication describing validation of a previously-defined
155 model on entirely new data from different centres⁴⁰. Out-of-sample validation is crucial for a
156 model that would be useful for different cohorts worldwide.

157 In the studies presented in Table 1, there seems to be a trend of an inverse relationship
158 between the sample size and the model accuracy. This is difficult to quantify since the accuracy
159 metrics are different for different approaches, but it suggests over-fitting in studies with small
160 sample sizes. In studies that do have larger sample sizes and even external cross-validation, the

161 accuracy is lower, suggesting there is room for improvement before these tools are incorporated
162 into clinical practice.

163 Missing data is a common problem in clinical datasets, and it is important that modelling studies
164 report how they handle missing data⁴¹, as different methods of imputation can affect
165 conclusions in different ways⁴². Eight of the studies in Table 1 do not describe how they handle
166 missing data. In the other studies, the authors either entirely exclude patients with missing data
167 from analysis, or they use the recommended imputation approach of imputing input variables
168 but not outcomes²².

169 Studies that have built predictive models with clinical data only have achieved some degree of
170 prediction accuracy^{29,34,39,40}. The most rigorously validated is the 'DBS-PREDICT' model, which
171 achieved 78% diagnostic accuracy between strong and weak responders in the initial patient
172 cohort, and was then validated across 6 different centres with a diagnostic accuracy of 73-77%
173 (Table 1)^{34,40}. The other two models with large numbers of patients tested using fewer input
174 measures or non-machine learning statistical methods to achieve similar binary prediction
175 accuracy²⁹, or predict exact outcome scores³⁹. The highly weighted features in these models are
176 consistent with those described by correlation studies, i.e. the age at surgery, duration of
177 symptoms and levodopa-responsiveness. Given the large numbers of patients and strong
178 validation, the accuracy of these studies likely represents a ceiling in the predictive ability of
179 simple clinical data. For higher accuracy and non-binarized outcomes it is likely necessary to add
180 inputs from other sources.

181 Adding structural MRI data to clinical data generally improves the accuracy of predictive models,
182 but studies must reduce the total possible radiomic inputs to not have vastly more inputs than

183 samples and thus over-fit the model²². Some studies achieve this by only focusing on select
184 anatomical regions^{7,28,30}, or only measures like cortical thickness or volumes of sub-cortical
185 structures^{18,27}. Even in these cases, some pre-processing step is required to select the most
186 relevant features, such as recursive feature elimination³⁰, LASSO³⁷, maximum relevancy
187 minimum redundancy²⁵, Boruta²⁵ or random forest³². Literature-based feature reduction can
188 also be performed by using information from other studies that report correlations rather than
189 building statistical models. For example, cortical thickness in the pre-motor and motor cortex,
190 grey matter volume in left superior frontal gyrus, thalamic volume, ventricular volume and
191 anterior cingulate volume are good candidates based on existing studies^{21,43-45}. Further, the
192 predictive value of the occipital cortex and cerebellum may be underestimated due to their
193 exclusion from MRI analyses that leave out poorly-captured parts of the brain^{21,46}.

194 Table 1: Published predictive models of motor outcomes from deep brain stimulation for Parkinson’s disease. Studies are sorted alphabetically by first author.
 195 Prediction type descriptions are prefaced by ‘classification’ or ‘regression’ to indicate binary or continuous prediction types. AUC = area under the curve, L-dopa
 196 = levodopa, LASSO = least absolute shrinkage and selection operator, LGB = light gradient boosting, MDS = Movement disorder society (updated UPDRS), MRI =
 197 magnetic resonance imaging, MSE = mean squared error, NPV = negative predictive value, PKG = Parkinson’s Kinetigraph, PPV = positive predictive value, SVM =
 198 support vector machine, UPDRS = Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale, VTA = volume of tissue activated

Author	Year	N	Data inputs	Model type	Prediction type	Accuracy	Imputation of missing data	Validation	Baseline normalization
Amprimo et al ²⁵	2025	50	Clinical data and gait parameters from motion capture.	Support vector machine, AdaBoost, light gradient boosting and extreme gradient boosting.	Classification. Specifically predicting gait outcomes, into 2 clusters based on change in gait metrics. 6 months after surgery.	Best model is LGB with all data (clinical and gait): weighted sensitivity 83.50.	Not mentioned, but they did also create synthetic data for training with SMOTE.	Leave-one-out cross validation.	Outcome is not UDPRS, but the change in gait metrics used to define the clusters are not baseline-corrected.
Biesheuvel et al ³⁹	2025	408	Clinical data.	Linear regression, Random Forest, LASSO.	Regression. Exact scores for total MDS-UPDRS III and sub-scores, 12 months after surgery.	R ² for total MDS-UPDRS III = 0.3, tremor = 0.29, axial = 0.31, bradykinesia/rigidity = 0.25.	Imputation with Scikit-learn ‘Iterative Imputer’.	Held out a test set from the model development (~20% of data).	Predict exact outcomes to avoid measures of relative improvement.
Chen et al ³⁷	2022	94	Clinical data, brain-wide MRI measures of cortical thickness, grey matter volume, white matter volume and VTA.	Support vector machine.	Regression. Predict UPDRS III percentage improvement, with confidence intervals. 1 month after surgery.	SVM with clinical, VTA and MRI has r=0.5678, deviations from actual scores of 11.4±10.9%.	Not mentioned.	Held out a test set from the model development (~25% of data).	Not clear, but pre-operative score is not used as a predictor, only medication response.

Diao et al ³⁸	2024	138	Clinical and MRI. Use the 6 top edges from structural networks and intracranial volume as inputs.	Perceptron classifier, XGBoost.	Both classification and regression. Predict 'improvement percentage' at 12 months after surgery.	Perceptron classifier, AUC 0.8, XGBoost R = 0.67, MSE 0.06.	Not mentioned.	Separated into 75% training and 25% validation set.	Did not use baseline motor or L-dopa response as an input.
Geraedts et al ³⁵	2023	75	Clinical data and Parkinson's Kinetigraph.	Continuous: Multiple linear regression, Binary: Logistic regression.	Both classification and regression. Compare DBS-only and optimal therapy improvement, 1 year after surgery.	Multivariate with PKG data: R ² = 0.478, with L-dopa test R ² = 0.470 AUC of PKG model 0.659, of L-dopa model 0.695.	Not described, but they note inherent missing data.	None.	Baseline correction of outcomes.
Habets et al ³⁴	2020	89	Clinical only, but including cognitive measures like Stroop and language tests.	Logistic regression.	Classification. Binary outcome based on UPDRS II, III and IV at 1 year after surgery.	PPV 0.63 and NPV of 0.88. Classification accuracy 78%.	Yes, using random forest, only for pre-operative values.	5-fold validation so each patient is used for testing exactly once.	No, decision tree is based on absolute differences. UPDRS IV and III pre-surgical scores contribute the most to model performance.
Habets et al ⁴⁰	2021	322	Clinical only, just 11 inputs.	Logistic regression.	Classification. Binary outcome based on UPDRS II, III and IV at 1 year after surgery.	PPV 0.62, NPV 0.79. Classification accuracy 77%.	Not mentioned, only included patients with all data?	Using previously defined model on cohorts from 6 centres in 3 continents.	No, as above.

Haliasos et al ²⁶	2024	120	Clinical and seven radiomics features (T1 whole-brain measures).	Random forest, logistic regression, naive Bayes, support vector machine, K-nearest neighbours.	Classification. Binary threshold is 5-point change on UPDRS III medication-on scores at 1 year after surgery.	Logistic regression: PPV 0.88 and NPV 0.86. Random forest: PPV 0.96 and NPV 0.94.	Excluded patients with missing MRI data.	Bootstrapping: iteratively re-dividing the dataset into training and test data.	Not handled (And the most strongly weighted factor is the pre-surgery UPDRS III med-on score).
Krause et al ²⁷	2022	105	Clinical (wider range of data than typical), and some MRI measures (structure volumes).	Support vector machine, logistic regression, k-neighbors, random forest classifiers.	Classification. Both binary and 3-group. Time to follow-up not clear.	Support vector performs the best: 81.7% accuracy for binary, 56.9% precision for multi-class.	Impute scalar variables with mean (not for med-on UPDRS III), label 'missing' for categorical.	10-fold hold-out testing (presumably so each patient is in the test pool once).	Not corrected for.
Li et al ⁴⁷	2024	39	Resting fMRI delta controllability.	Support vector regression.	Regression. Change in UPDRS III score, 1 month after surgery	For STN target R=0.514, for GPi target R=0.705	Excluded patients with missing data.	Leave-one-out cross-validation.	Baseline corrected.
Liu et al ³⁰	2021	33	10 MRI features specifically of the substantia nigra, and pre-operative levodopa responsiveness.	Logistic regression, based either on radiomics, levodopa responsiveness or both.	Classification. Binary threshold of 30% improvement on MDS-UPDRS III score 6 months after surgery, excluding tremor scores.	Radiomics only: 82% accuracy, radiomics + levodopa response 74%, levodopa alone 58%.	Not mentioned.	Leave-one-out cross-validation.	Not corrected for.
Peralta et al ⁷	2021	196	Clinical data and striatal shape vectors from T1-weighted MRI.	'PassFlow': Artificial neural network + support vector machine, and	Regression. Predict exact values on various metrics including UPDRS III, follow-	R for UPDRS III with med-off is >0.5 for 3 and 6 months, ~0.4	Previously defined artificial neural network to	50-fold cross-validation or leave one out cross validation if	Not clear.

				comparison to linear regression.	up is up to 3 years.	at 1 year and 0.3 at 3 years.	impute variables.	fewer than 50 scores available.	
Saudargiene et al ²⁸	2022	34	20 features from MRI of the amygdala and hippocampus. Clinical features not included.	Logistic regression, deep neural network, SVM, decision tree, linear discriminant, naive Bayes, autoencoder.	Classification. Binary outcomes of Parkinson's disease composite scale scores 6 months after surgery.	Logistic regression: accuracy 96.65%, deep neural network accuracy 87.25%.	Not mentioned.	Separated into 85% training and 15% test data (i.e. very few poor outcome patients). 1000 bootstrapped repetitions.	Clinical features not used as inputs.
Wang et al ³²	2021	55	Functional networks from fMRI (without clinical features).	Ridge regression, 4 models of different hemisphere connections.	Regression. Scalar prediction of improvement in UPDRS III, 6 months after surgery.	Best model is right hemisphere (r = 0.37).	Not mentioned.	Nested leave-one-out cross-validation.	Pre-operative score not used as a predictor.
Wang et al ³⁶	2025	93	Clinical data and structural networks from diffusion tensor imaging.	Multiple linear regression.	Regression. Scalar prediction of change in UPDRS III, 1 month after surgery.	Clinical + structural model gives r = 0.715, R ² = 0.534.	Not mentioned.	None.	Baseline corrected.
Wolke et al ²⁹	2023	429	Clinical data only, trying to minimise inputs and compare statistical methods to machine learning.	Continuous: Linear model, Xgradient boosting tree model, support vector machine Binary: logistic regression.	Both classification and regression. Predict the absolute and relative outcome. 6-12 months after surgery.	Linear model: absolute R ² = 0.41, relative R ² = 0.14. Logistic regression: 72% or 78% accuracy.	No, where data is missing for a measure, they exclude patients for that test.	Data from 3 centres, pooled for the model. SMOTE 10-fold cross-validation used. Centre and scale data before training.	Predict both absolute and relative values for improvement and L-dopa response.

Younce et al ³³	2025	65	Clinical, structural MRI and fMRI.	Relaxed LASSO regression.	Regression. Scalar prediction of change in UPDRS III, 12 months after surgery.	Clinical and MRI data $R^2 = 0.315$.	Exclusion of patients missing data.	Leave-one-out cross-validation.	Corrected according to Zaidel et al.
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200 Output variables: what to predict?

201 The most important decision in designing an outcome prediction model is defining what the
202 output variable to be predicted is. Considering we focus here on motor outcomes, this is most
203 commonly a score on the unified Parkinson's disease rating scale (UPDRS) III⁴⁸ or the movement
204 disorder society (MDS)-UPDRS III⁴⁹ tests of motor function. However, these tests can be further
205 broken down into sub-categories such as tremor, bradykinesia, posture/gait and rigidity⁵⁰, and a
206 more nuanced prediction may be useful considering each patient is affected by different motor
207 aspects to different degrees. Tremor, for example, generally has the most positive impact from
208 DBS, and other aspects such as gait instability (which are mediated through non-dopaminergic
209 pathways⁵¹) do not show as much improvement with DBS⁵². For example, a tremor-dominant
210 patient only stands to gain functionality in the tremor-related sections of the UPDRS-III, so their
211 change in motor performance may be smaller than that of a patient with a mixed phenotype,
212 even if their motor symptoms are completely resolved. It would be useful for patients and
213 clinicians to assess which aspects of their motor activity are likely to be improved by DBS.
214 Further, the effects of DBS can be compared to pre-surgery or stimulation off post-surgery, and
215 whether in the presence or absence of supplementary dopaminergic medication (Figure 2). The
216 pure effect of DBS alone is measured in the absence of medication, compared to the motor
217 performance in the absence of medication either before the surgery or after turning off the
218 stimulation. There can be microlesion effects from surgery⁵³, and stimulation may produce
219 some degree of protective effect after being switched off, so it is most typical to compare to the
220 pre-surgery state. This comparison gives a read-out of the motor improvement produced by DBS

221 compared to the patient's pre-surgery unmedicated state. For most patients, this comparison
 222 shows a sizeable improvement. However, there is also an argument for comparing the
 223 medication-on states, as these represent the actual condition the patient lives with, and is
 224 therefore an outcome of interest to the clinician and patient. Motor performance improvement
 225 with DBS stimulation combined with medication is not as dramatic compared to pre-surgery
 226 with medication, but this change also typically represents an opportunity to drastically reduce
 227 the medication dosage, transferring the major part of the treatment to consistent stimulation
 228 instead of intermittent medication.

229 *Figure 2: Methods to assess motor outcomes. Before surgery, the motor performance with and*
 230 *without levodopa treatment can be compared. After surgery, motor performance with both DBS*
 231 *stimulation and medication off can be compared to stimulation only or stimulation and*
 232 *medication combined. The improvement with DBS can therefore be described as the*
 233 *improvement with stimulation (and without medication) compared to either the pre-surgery*
 234 *medication off condition, or the post-surgery medication and DBS off condition. Alternatively, to*
 235 *describe the condition the patient will live with, the optimal treatment condition before and*
 236 *after surgery should be compared. DBS = deep brain stimulation, L-dopa = Levodopa.*

237 A model may aim to predict the exact UPDRS III score with DBS, but many models instead
238 predict the difference in the motor score compared to the relevant pre-surgery condition (Table
239 1). In this case it is crucial to carefully consider how to implement the pre-operative motor score
240 or responsiveness to Levodopa as a predictor in the model⁵⁴. Because of the ceiling effect on
241 outcome scores (they cannot improve beyond 0: 'no disability'), the variance in the change in
242 performance is mainly driven by the variance in initial scores, so the initial performance or pre-
243 surgery levodopa responsive is correlated to the change without actually being an accurate
244 predictor^{54,55}. A recommended method for avoiding spurious correlations is using relative rather
245 than absolute values, e.g. dividing by the baseline medication-off score⁵⁴. This generally retains
246 a correlation between relative baseline and outcome scores, but not to the same extent as using
247 the absolute value^{24,29}. An assessment of whether this baseline correction is performed is
248 included in Table 1.

249 There is also a question of how to present predicted outcomes. Some studies have used a
250 binarized approach of good vs poor DBS outcome, as it relates to the binary clinical decision to
251 operate or not^{26-30,40}. Binarizing the outcome is suited to using a logistic regression or other
252 classification approaches for the model, and allows the model accuracy to be measured in terms
253 of the sensitivity (identification of good responders) and specificity (identification of poor
254 responders). However, it requires setting a threshold of what outcome is sufficient to be
255 classified as 'good', and a binary outcome does not give information on how close to this
256 threshold a prediction is^{7,25}. Further, these studies are generally retrospective, so patients who
257 are not good candidates for DBS in the first place are not included. This skew makes the
258 classification task more difficult, as the potential candidates with the worst outcomes are not

259 present in the dataset. The division between good and poor outcomes is therefore unequal, and
260 studies should employ methods to adjust for class imbalance^{28,34}. Instead, providing clinicians
261 with an estimated outcome motor score³⁹ or estimated improvement with a confidence range³⁷
262 would enable them to make informed judgements, taking into account the uncertainty of the
263 model.

264 As well as the output being presented in a way that is clinically interpretable, the factors that
265 lead to the model producing that output should be able to be made clear to clinicians. For
266 example, complex radiomics features from MRI data may contribute to a model with good
267 predictive performance²⁶, but they should be described in a way that is anatomically meaningful
268 to clinicians. The rise of machine learning approaches in medical research includes applications
269 to Parkinson's research and outcome prediction¹¹. However, in the case of predictive models
270 built with machine learning approaches, 'white-box' models are preferable to 'black-box' ones
271 because the factors that influenced the decision can be examined, even if 'black-box' models
272 may achieve higher accuracy²⁶.

273 Finally, a model should be built to be able to produce predictions for counselling individual
274 patients, so predictions should not be restricted to group-level estimates. An example of the
275 type of output statements that could be useful to clinicians are presented in Figure 3.

276 Input variables: candidate modalities of predictive data

277 Clinical and demographic data

278 A model based solely on data collected from clinical visits during standard screening for DBS
279 surgery eligibility is very appealing as the input data are readily available and clinically

280 interpretable. Several studies have compared outcomes to pre-surgical clinical data^{23,56-60}, and
281 others have tested building models to predict outcomes^{25,29,31,34,39,40}. Generally, age at surgery
282 and disease duration before surgery are correlated with the clinical outcome, with older
283 patients having worse outcomes, and those with longer disease duration having better
284 outcomes (presumably due to slower disease progression)^{4,61}. An important clinical predictor is
285 the Levodopa response before surgery (the difference between motor performance with and
286 without medication). Patients with good responsiveness to Levodopa are considered to be good
287 candidates for DBS¹, but as mentioned above its predictive potential can be overestimated using
288 absolute values^{54,55}. However, a recent meta-analysis using the more statistically sound
289 approach of comparing relative improvement showed that the Levodopa response before
290 surgery correlates to the motor outcomes at 6 months and 12 months after surgery, but not at 2
291 to 8 years after surgery²⁴.

292 Cardiovascular function also appears to be important to DBS outcomes: the presence of
293 vascular abnormalities on the pre-operative MRI scan predicts worse outcomes^{4,23,62}, and higher
294 cardiac washout rate is correlated with better DBS outcomes⁶³.

295 Neurocognitive tests

296 While performance on cognitive tests would typically be considered as predictors of cognitive
297 outcomes, there is also evidence that better performance on tests of frontal lobe performance
298 correlates with better motor outcomes from DBS^{23,60,62}. Better performance on cognitive tests
299 may indicate better capacity of the brain to adapt to new conditions like the input of electrical
300 stimulation.

301 *Figure 3: Schematic of possible predictive model. Some combination of the pre-surgical clinical*
 302 *factors discussed in this review can be used as inputs, with clinical and demographic data as a*
 303 *starting point. Researchers should then consider how the predictions would be presented to the*
 304 *clinician. In the case of a binary outcome, this would be the chosen category and some measure*
 305 *of confidence in the classification, such as likelihood of being classified as a ‘good responder’, or*
 306 *the log odds between the two outcomes. For a numeric estimate, either the absolute motor*
 307 *questionnaire score or the relative improvement could be reported, with a range indicating the*
 308 *accuracy of the prediction. Output can also be broken down into sub-categories of motor*
 309 *performance. To aid clinician understanding of the reasoning behind predictions, a summary of*
 310 *the most highly-weighted factors influencing the model for that patient can be reported. A more*
 311 *complex model could also provide predictions for several timepoints after surgery to model the*
 312 *patient’s trajectory over time.*

313 Structural MRI data

314 Static MRI images are already routinely collected as part of the surgical planning process (to
315 check for any abnormalities that would represent unacceptable risk for brain surgery)¹. If this
316 data can be leveraged to also predict the efficacy of DBS for a patient, it would therefore
317 minimally impact the existing clinical workflow. A range of studies have attempted to correlate
318 various aspects of MRI images to motor outcomes, recent reviews have shown there is little
319 cohesion in the results^{21,43}. This is partially due to inconsistencies in the outcome metric that
320 studies attempt to predict, and also because studies do not use the same list of candidate MRI
321 features⁴³.

322 The models presented in Table 1 find important features from MRI data that include the right
323 inferior precentral area³⁷, structural covariance between the left superior frontal gyrus and the
324 right insular cortex, and some cerebellar regions³⁸, second-order measures of whole-brain
325 white-matter²⁶, left putamen volume²⁷ and striatal shape⁷.

326 The extent of Parkinsonian degeneration of the substantia nigra can be estimated with T2-
327 relaxometry to measure iron levels, and this may also be an important predictor for the
328 amenability of the network to improvement with DBS^{30,64}.

329 Structural connectivity of brain networks can also be estimated with diffusion tensor imaging
330 (though this is not routinely collected before DBS surgery). One study found that incorporating
331 this data can improve the performance of a clinical predictive model for the initial outcome of
332 DBS³⁶. The most important connectivity link was between the left superior frontal gyrus and left
333 medial frontal gyrus.

334 Kinematics

335 Better characterisation of motor symptoms beyond the standard UPDRS III or MDS-UPDRS III
336 rating scales can be achieved by using data-driven assessment of kinematics. This may involve
337 gait assessment from video capture, or the use of wearable sensors. The latter enables data
338 collection over a wider period of time rather than the brief snapshot afforded to clinicians
339 during a clinical visit. Wearable sensors are not routinely incorporated into clinical assessment,
340 but they are a low-cost measure than can be added to clinical workflows without much
341 difficulty⁶⁵. However, one study which did incorporate data from such wearable sensors did not
342 find that it improved predictions of overall motor outcomes by a multivariate linear model
343 beyond that of standard clinical data³⁵. Data from these sensors may be more effective for
344 describing phenotypes in specific aspects of movement, but not others, and therefore are not
345 useful for predicting changes in the sum of scores from rating scales. Motion capture can give
346 better assessment particularly of gait, and these measures in the levodopa-on state show
347 promise as being predictive of gait outcomes from DBS⁶⁶. Indeed, a recent model incorporating
348 gait data from motion capture found that it can aid prediction of the change to gait parameters
349 from DBS²⁵. For patients and clinicians who are specifically interested in the effects of DBS on
350 gait, these measures give better information than the gait-related questions on motor rating
351 questionnaires.

352 Functional connectivity

353 Measures of functional brain activity are powerful data that represent the very network activity
354 that DBS aims to manipulate. Collecting fMRI data is expensive and not typically involved in the

355 standard clinical pipeline, but if it proves to have strong predictive power for DBS outcomes
356 then incorporating it would be worthwhile. A recent model incorporating functional
357 connectivity data from resting-state fMRI did find that it improved predictive accuracy beyond
358 clinical data alone³³. Principal components of the FC made up 5 of the 9 selected factors for the
359 combined model. Another model specifically focused on the cortico-striatal-thalamic-cortical
360 motor loop, and found the pre-operative change in network controllability of the thalamus with
361 medication was the most relevant to the motor outcome⁴⁷.

362 The same problems with structural MRI studies also apply to these functional models, but to a
363 greater extent: the data has even higher dimensionality and there are fewer studies to compare
364 between to hope to find convergence. Further, using factor reduction methods such as principal
365 component analysis produces predictors that are unlikely to be able to generalise to other
366 datasets. Measures of functional activity are therefore a fascinating avenue for outcome
367 prediction, but there is much work to be done before we can identify factors that will generalise
368 across the Parkinson's population.

369 Some methods of developing and testing these models may be very computationally intensive,
370 but ideally, they should then produce a model that does not require a large amount of
371 computational power to apply to new patients. A model that requires intensive pre-processing
372 of imaging data before inputting the features to the model is unrealistic for clinical use.

373 Functional connectivity could also be measured by electroencephalography (EEG) or
374 magnetoencephalography (MEG). One study used MEG activity to predict motor outcomes
375 based on the functional connectivity of the targeted area after DBS electrode implantation¹⁵,
376 but we did not find studies using these techniques pre-operatively to predict outcomes. While

377 they are also not part of routine collection, EEG in particular may represent a more cost-
378 effective measure of functional connectivity than fMRI and it remains to be seen whether pre-
379 operative activity signatures from these modalities have predictive power for motor outcomes.

380 Genetics

381 Some proportion of Parkinson's patients who receive DBS treatment will be carriers of genetic
382 mutations that may affect the degree of motor improvement. For example, patients with
383 mutations in the GBA gene tend to have good motor outcomes, albeit poor cognitive
384 outcomes^{67,68}. Those with mutations in PRKN tend to have younger onset of Parkinson's, which
385 may relate to their having good motor outcomes from DBS, but they do have poor non-motor
386 outcomes⁶⁸. However, mutations in SNCA appear to have poor motor outcomes, so the specific
387 gene which is mutated may affect the response to DBS in opposite directions⁶⁸. The evidence for
388 each gene is quite scarce, which makes it difficult to draw conclusions about interactions
389 between certain mutations and DBS outcomes⁶⁷. Although polygenic risk scores are an
390 attractive candidate input to predictive models of DBS outcomes, existing models are already
391 typically under-powered with regards to number of patients and genetic labelling would only
392 apply to a subset of patients. A very large cohort would be required to test the appropriate
393 weight to assign various genetic factors.

394 Validation and reproducibility

395 The current landscape of DBS outcome prediction does not show a great degree of cohesion
396 amongst results from different studies. This is partially due to the approach taken by many of
397 these studies. Most of the studies use small cohorts from a single centre, and do not use hold-

398 out testing data. External validation such as in Habets et al⁴⁰ is a crucial step for confirming the
399 performance of predictive models before they can be expected to be generalisable to clinics
400 worldwide^{21,22}. Models trained on retrospective data also necessarily only include patients who
401 were deemed good candidates for DBS. It is therefore not clear how they may perform on the
402 general population.

403 External validation data can be difficult to come by, so public availability of datasets (while
404 maintaining patient confidentiality) for cross-validating models would greatly assist the
405 endeavours of this field. There are some projects which offer to provide clinical data on request,
406 but these do not currently include neuroimaging data^{39,69}. Factors such as MRI acquisition
407 parameters and pharmaceutical prescription approaches can differ greatly between centres in
408 different countries⁴⁰, so a globally useful predictive model needs to be able to generalise across
409 these differences. Incorporating methods to control for site effects will therefore also be an
410 important step, particularly if neuroimaging data is part of the inputs⁷⁰. Very few of the studies
411 we assessed made their models available for other researchers to test on their own data. As
412 well as being important for open science, this approach would make it more feasible for cross-
413 validation studies to be conducted, or even better, for different published models to be
414 compared on the same validation dataset.

415 Conclusions

416 We have identified 17 studies that have aimed to build predictive models of motor outcomes
417 from deep brain stimulation for Parkinson's disease. They vary widely in terms of their input
418 data, sample sizes, validation rigour and prediction accuracy. Lacking amongst these studies are

419 predictions of outcomes beyond the first year after surgery, and cross-validation of models on
420 external datasets. These are all retrospective studies, so the datasets only include people who
421 were considered good candidates for DBS. This makes the task of separating good and poor
422 responders difficult, and means models may not generalise to the wider Parkinson's population.
423 Generally, adding data from other modalities to basic clinical and demographic data stands to
424 produce models with higher accuracy, but future models need to also have higher numbers of
425 participants to incorporate these extra factors in a statistically sound manner. Future studies
426 should also follow recommendations from Poldrack et al²² and the TRIPOD statement⁴¹ in order
427 to build models that incorporate best practice and report their findings transparently. We have
428 created a schematic in Figure 3 to illustrate hypothetical model inputs and outputs for
429 researchers to consider when designing future predictive models.

430 Many studies testing individual predictors with limited accuracy have made clear that outcome
431 prediction for DBS must involve integrating predictors that carry information about different
432 functional domains (Figure 2). A holistic view of outcome predictors is necessary since DBS acts
433 on interacting systems¹⁰ in a highly variable and inherently unstable pathological environment.
434 Adding inputs from rich data sources such as neuroimaging, kinematics and genetics leads to a
435 problem for building predictive models of having too many input factors for the number of
436 patients (the curse of dimensionality). While there are several statistical methods for reducing
437 dimensions, researchers can also use literature-based dimensionality reduction as well as
438 consider using these data to build integrative metrics such as 'nigrostriatal integrity' or 'frontal
439 connectivity'. This approach can serve the dual purpose of reducing the number of inputs to the

440 model and generalising across patient-specific pathology that leads to similar physiological
441 outcomes.

442 We believe this review provides a framework for future studies to produce robustly
443 generalisable predictive models for DBS outcomes, which are likely to be taken up for clinical
444 use. In particular, the inputs and outputs should be clinically interpretable, and the model
445 should be able to generalise to data from different centres. Ideally, actual MDS-UPDRS III scores
446 should be predicted, over a range of time-points after DBS surgery. This will enable clinicians to
447 make their own decision about what represents a likely ‘good’ outcome. To aid researchers
448 comparing between and building on predictive models, the strategies for dealing with missing
449 data, correcting for baseline scores, and validating the model should be clearly described,
450 metrics of fit accuracy should be reported, and models should be made available to other
451 researchers. Data should also be made available (at least within consortia), to enable
452 researchers to test their models on data from external centres.

453

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463 1. Review: A. Conception, B. Search and abstract screening, C. Assessment of studies

464 2. Manuscript preparation: A. Writing of the main text, B. Figures, C. Review and critique.

465 MW: 1A, 1B, 1C, 2A, 2B.

466 DK: 2C.

467 EB: 2B, 2C.

468 PF: 1A, 2C.

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